

**Ovid MEDLINE(R) Epub Ahead of Print, In-Process & Other Non-Indexed Citations,
Ovid MEDLINE(R) Daily and Ovid MEDLINE(R) 1946 to Present. Searched using the
OvidSP platform on [19/02/2019; 12:50]**

<u>Number</u>	<u>Medline Search term</u>	<u>Terms from 1st verison of search that will be captured by this term</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	mendelian random*.mp.		Free text keywords for MR
2	instrumental variable*.mp.	instrumental variable analysis.mp.	
3	causal ass*.mp.		
4	causal anal*.mp.		
5	genetic instrument.mp.		
6	genetic epidemiology.mp.		
7	exp Molecular Epidemiology/	Covers: Molecular Epidemiology (11086 hits) Genome Wide Association Studies (21655 hits) Mendelian Randomisation Studies (525 hits)	MeSH Term for MR Need to decide how broad or restrictive you want this to be, as the choice will stongly affect how many records are retrieved. (ML: we shouldnt include genome wide associantiont study, instead if they do an MR but dont call it MR in a GWAS paper they publish it should come p through 'causal anal/ass*' . but if there arent that many additional papers as a result of including GWAS then yeah do it.
8	or/1-6	excluding molecular epidemiology	
9	or/1-7	including molecular epidemiology	Combined free text and MeSH terms for MR using OR
10	body mass*.mp.		Free text keywords for adiposity/adiposity measures
11	bmi.mp.		
12	quetelet*.mp.		

13	weight.mp.	body weight.mp. birth weight.mp. birthweight.mp fetal weight.mp. foetal weight.mp thinness.mp. under weight.mp. underweight.mp. normal weight.mp. normalweight.mp. over weight.mp. overweight.mp. under-weight.mp normal-weight.mp over-weight.mp weight gain.mp weight loss.mp weight change.mp weight reduction.mp	
14	obes*.mp	obesity, abdominal.mp. obesity, metabolically benign.mp. obesity, morbid.mp. clinically obese.mp. morbidly obese.mp. paediatric obesity.mp. pediatric obesity.mp. obesity, clinical.mp	
15	exp Obesity/		
16	waist circumference.mp.		
17	hip circumference.mp.		
18	waist height ratio.mp.	waist-height ratio.mp.	
19	waist:height ratio.mp.		

20	height waist ratio.mp.	height-waist ratio.mp.	
21	height:waist ratio.mp.		
22	waist hip ratio.mp.	waist-hip ratio.mp.	
23	waist:hip ratio.mp.		
24	waist-to-hip.mp		
25	WHR.mp		
26	waist adj2 ratio.mp.		
27	hip waist ratio.mp.	hip-waist ratio.mp.	
28	hip:waist ratio.mp.		
29	hip-to-waist.mp		
30	sagittal abdominal diameter.mp.	sagittal-abdominal diameter.mp.	
31	fat.mp.	whole body fat free mass.mp. whole-body fat free mass.mp. whole-body-fat free mass.mp. whole-body-fat-free mass.mp. whole-body-fat-free-mass.mp. whole body-fat free mass.mp. whole body-fat-free mass.mp. whole body fat-free mass.mp. whole body fat-free-mass.mp. whole body fat free-mass.mp. whole-body fat-free mass.mp. whole-body fat-free-mass.mp. whole-body fat free-mass.mp. whole-body fat-free mass.mp. whole-body fat free-mass.mp. lean vs.	

		<p>fat mass.mp. lean ?? fat mass.mp. lean "near" fat mass.mp. fat tissue.mp. abdominal fat.mp. android fat.mp. gynoid fat.mp. intra- abdominal fat.mp. subcutaneous adipose tissue.mp. subcutaneous fat.mp. visceral fat.mp. fat depos*.mp fat distribution.mp. "body fat distribution.mp. body-fat distribution.mp. body fat- distribution.mp. body-fat- distribution.mp. fat- distribution.mp. fat mass index.mp.</p>	
32	lean adj3 mass.mp.	<p>lean-mass.mp. lean body mass.mp. lean-body mass.mp. lean body-mass.mp. lean-body-mass.mp.</p>	
33	bioelectrical impedance*.mp.	<p>bioelectrical impedance analysis.mp.</p>	
34	electric impedance.mp.		
35	impedance of*.mp.		
36	adipos*.mp.		
37	subcutaneous adipose tissue.mp.		
38	subcutaneous visceral ratio.mp.	subcutaneous- visceral ratio	

39	visceral adipose tissue.mp.		
40	visceral subcutaneous ratio.mp.	visceral-subcutaneous ratio.mp	
41	vat sat ratio.mp.		
42	fat mass index.mp.		
43	FMI.mp.		
44	body composition.mp.		
45	somatotypes.mp.		
46	body size.mp.		
47	overeate*.mp		
48	lipid accumulation product.mp.		
49	metabolic syndrome.mp.		
50	or/10-49		Combined free text terms for adiposity/adiposity measures using OR
51	exp "Body Weights and Measures"/	Covers: Body Fat Distribution Adiposity Body Mass Index Body Size Body Height Crown-Rump Length Body Weight Birth Weight Fetal Weight Ideal Body Weight Overweight Obesity Obesity, Abdominal Obesity, Metabolically Benign Obesity, Morbid Pediatric Obesity Thinness Sagittal Abdominal Diameter	MeSH Terms for adiposity/adiposity measures

		<p>Waist Circumference Waist-Height Ratio Body Surface Area Organ Size Axial Length, Eye Skinfold Thickness Waist-Hip Ratio</p>	
52	exp Body Weight/		
53	exp Electrical Impedance/		
54	exp Physical Appearance, Body/		
55	exp Absorptiometry, Photon/	<p>absorptiometries, dpx absorptiometry, dpx absorptiometry, dual energy radiographic absorptiometry, dual energy x ray absorptiometry, dual x ray absorptiometry, dual x-ray absorptiometry, dual-energy radiographic absorptiometry, dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry, dual-photon absorptiometry, photon absorptiometry, single-photon absorptiometry, x ray absorptiometry, x- ray dexa scan dexa scans</p>	

		<p>dpx absorptiometry dxa scan dxa scans densitometry, x ray densitometry, x-ray densitometry, xray dual energy radiographic absorptiometry dual energy x ray absorptiometry dual energy x ray absorptiometry scan dual photon absorptiometry dual x ray absorptiometry dual x-ray absorptiometry dual-energy radiographic absorptiometry dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry scan dual-photon absorptiometry photodensitometry, x ray photodensitometry, x-ray photon absorptiometry radiographic absorptiometry, dual energy radiographic absorptiometry, dual-energy scan, dxa scan, dxa scans, dxa</p>	
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		<p>scans, dxa single photon absorptiometry single-photon absorptiometry x ray absorptiometry x ray absorptiometry, dual energy x ray photodensitometry x-ray absorptiometry x-ray absorptiometry, dual x-ray absorptiometry, dual-energy x-ray densitometry x-ray photodensitometry xray densitometry</p>	
56	<p>exp Positron Emission Tomography Computed Tomography/</p>	<p>ct petct pet scansct pet scansct petsct scan, petct scans, petpet, ctpet ct scanpet ct scanspet scan, ctpet scans, ctpet-ctpet-ct scanpet-ct scanspets, ctpositron emission tomography computed tomographypositron emission tomography- computed tomographyscan, ct petscan, pet ctscan, pet-ctscans, ct</p>	

		petscans, pet ctscans, pet-ct	
57	or/51-56		Combined MeSH terms for adiposity/adiposity measures using OR
58	50 or 57		Combined free text and MeSH terms for adiposity/adiposity measures using OR
59	8 and 58	same number of hits as 8 so by 'AND' of all MR terms except GWAS and all adiposity terms you dont remove any papers in which MR is mentioned	Combined free text and MeSH terms for MR and adiposity/adiposity measures using AND
60	9 and 58		no mol epi included

Embase 1974 to 2019 Searched using the OvidSP platform on [19/02/2019; 12:01]

<u>Number</u>	<u>Embase Search term</u>	<u>Terms from 1st version of search that will be captured by this term</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	mendelian random*.mp.		Free text keywords for MR
2	instrumental variable*.mp.		
3	causal ass*.mp.		
4	causal anal*.mp.		
5	genetic instrument.mp.		
6	genetic epidemiology.mp.		
7	exp Molecular Epidemiology/	epidemiology, molecular History: 2010 Old preferred term: epidemiology [HSW]	EMBASE terms for MR
8	exp genome-wide association study/	genome wide association study History: 2016-05-01 Old preferred term: genetic association [HSW]	
9	exp genetic association study/	genetic association studies [MeSH Descriptor] History: 2016-05-01 Old preferred term: genetic association [HSW]	
10	or/ 1-6	excluding Molecular Epidemiology/GWAS/genetic association study	combined free text keywords for MR using OR
11	or/ 1-9	including Molecular Epidemiology/GWAS/genetic association study	combined free text keywords for MR and EMBASE terms for MR using OR
12	body mass*.mp.		Free text keywords for adiposity/adiposity measures
13	bmi.mp.		
14	quetelet*.mp.		
15	under weight.mp.		

16	normal weight.mp.		
17	normalweight.mp.		
18	over weight.mp.		
19	clinically obese.mp.		
20	morbidly obese.mp.		
21	obes*.mp		
22	waist circumference.mp		
23	hip circumference.mp		
24	waist:height ratio.mp.		
25	height waist ratio.mp.		
26	height:waist ratio.mp.		
27	waist:hip ratio.mp.		
28	waist-to-hip.mp		
29	WHR.mp		
30	waist adj2 ratio.mp.		
31	hip:waist ratio.mp.		
32	hip-to-waist.mp		
33	whole body fat free mass.mp.		
34	fat tissue.mp.		
35	abdominal fat.mp.		
36	android fat.mp.		
37	gynoid fat.mp.		
38	intra-abdominal fat.mp.		
39	fat depos*.mp		
40	fat distribution.mp.		
41	body fat distribution.mp.		

42	fat mass index.mp.		
43	FMI.mp.		
44	lean adj3 mass.mp.		
45	lean-mass.mp.		
46	bioelectrical impedance*.mp.		
47	electric impedance.mp.		
48	impedance of*.mp.		
49	adipos*.mp.		
50	subcutaneous adj3 ratio.mp.		
51	visceral adj3 ratio.mp.		
52	vat sat ratio.mp.		
53	overeat*.mp		
54	DEXA scan.mp.		
55	DXA scan.mp.		
56	DXA.mp.		
57	or/ 12-56		combined free text terms for adiposity/adiposity measures using OR
58	exp Weight/	na	combined EMBASE terms for adiposity/measure s of adiposity
59	exp Body Weight/	thinness [MeSH Descriptor] total body weight weight, body	
60	exp Birth Weight/	birthweight neonatal weight newborn weight weight,birth	
61	exp Fetus Weight/	embryo weight fetal body weight fetal weight [MeSH Descriptor] foetal body weight foetal weight	

		foetus weight weight, fetal weight, foetal	
62	exp Underweight/	weight insufficiency	
63	exp Weight Gain/	body weight gain weight increase	
64	exp Weight Reduction/	body weight loss body weight reduction weight decrease weight losing weight loss [MeSH Descriptor] weight reducing weight watching	
65	exp Weight Change/	body weight change body weight changes [MeSH Descriptor] History: 2006 Old preferred term: body weight disorder [HSW] weight changes	
66	exp Obesity/	adipose tissue hyperplasia adipositas adiposity [MeSH Descriptor] alimentary obesity body weight, excess fat overload syndrome nutritional obesity obesitas overweight [MeSH Descriptor]	
67	exp Abdominal Obesity/	abdominal adiposity obesity, abdominal [MeSH Descriptor]	
68	exp Metabolically Benign Obesity	obesity, metabolically benign [MeSH Descriptor]	
69	exp Morbid Obesity/	obesity, morbid [MeSH Descriptor] obesity, morbid	
70	exp Childhood Obesity/	paediatric obesity pediatric obesity [MeSH Descriptor]	
71	exp Waist Circumference/	waist size	
72	exp Hip Circumference/	na	

73	exp Waist to Height Ratio/	waist height ratio waist-height ratio [MeSH Descriptor]	
74	exp Waist Hip Ratio/	hip to waist ratio hip waist ratio waist to hip ratio waist-hip ratio [MeSH Descriptor]	
75	exp Sagittal abdominal Diameter/	na	
76	exp Fat/	fats [MeSH Descriptor] yellow fat	
77	exp Subcutaneous Fat	fat,subcutaneous subcutaneous adipose tissue subcutaneous fat tissue	
78	exp Intra-peritoneal Fat	abdominal visceral adipose tissue History: 2016-09-01 Old preferred term: intraabdominal fat [HSW] abdominal visceral fat History: 2016-09-01 Old preferred term: intraabdominal fat [HSW] intra-peritoneal adipose tissue intra-peritoneal fat intraperitoneal adipose tissue visceral abdominal adipose tissue History: 2016-09-01 Old preferred term: intraabdominal fat [HSW] visceral abdominal fat History: 2016-09-01 Old preferred term: intraabdominal fat [HSW] visceral adipose tissue History: 2016-09-01 Old preferred term: intraabdominal fat [HSW] visceral fat History: 2016-09-01 Old preferred term: intraabdominal fat [HSW]	

79	exp Body Fat Distribution	adipose tissue distribution fat tissue distribution fatty tissue distribution subcutaneous fat distribution visceral fat distribution	
80	exp Lean Body Weight	body lean mass body mass,lean body weight,lean lean body mass lean weight weight,lean	
81	exp Impedance/	electric impedance [MeSH Descriptor] electrical impedance input impedance	
82	exp Adipose Tissue/	fat tissue fatty tissue tissue,fat	
83	exp Body Composition/	composition,body	
84	exp Somatotype/	somatotypes [MeSH Descriptor]somatotyping	
85	exp Body Size/	na	
86	exp Lipid Accumulation Product Index/	LAP index (lipid) lipid accumulation product [MeSH Descriptor]	
87	exp Metabolic Syndrome X/	insulin resistance syndrome metabolic syndrome syndrome X, metabolic	
88	exp Body Mass/	BMI (body mass index) body ban mass body mass index [MeSH Descriptor] Quetelet index	
89	exp Body Height/	body length height,body length,body stature	
90	exp Crown Rump Length/	crown-rump length [MeSH Descriptor]	
91	exp Ideal Body Weight/	optimal body weight	

92	exp Body Surface/	area,body surface body surface area [MeSH Descriptor] surface,body	
93	exp Organ Size/	organ dimension organ volume	
94	exp Skinfold Thickness/	skin fold measurement skin fold thickness skin thickness skinfold measurement	
95	exp Absorptiometry/	na	
96	exp Dual Energy X Ray Absorptiometry/	absorptiometry,dual energy x ray dexa dual x ray absorptiometry	
97	exp positron emission tomography- computed tomography/	mputer assisted positron emission tomography History: 2017-01-01 Old preferred term: computer assisted emission tomography [HSW]positron emission computed tomography History: 2017-01-01 Old preferred term: computer assisted emission tomography [HSW]positron emission tomography computed tomography [MeSH Descriptor]positron emission tomography,computer assisted History: 2017-01-01 Old preferred term: computer assisted emission tomography [HSW]positron-emission tomography and computed tomography History: 2017-01- 01 Old preferred term: computer assisted emission tomography [HSW]	
98	ex positron emission tomography/	PET scan PET scanning positron emission	

		tomographic scan positron emission tomographic scanning positron tomography positron-emission tomography [MeSH Descriptor] tomography,positron	
99	or/ 58-98		Combined EMBASE terms for adiposity/adiposity measures using OR
100	57 or 99		Combined free text and EMBASE terms for adiposity/adiposity measures using OR
101	10 and 100		
102	11 and 100		

bioRxiv
search term
"mendelian randomisation"
"mendelian randomization"
"causal association"
"causal analysis"